

Displacement Trauma And Its Relationship For Life Orientation

Zalzalah Mahmood Abass

Article Info

Article History

Received:
April 25, 2021

Accepted:
July 03, 2021

Keywords :

Life Orientation , Forced Displacement, Displacement Trauma

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.5068187

Abstract

Forced displacement of the population is considered one of the grave violations under the Fourth Geneva Convention and the provision under the Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court, as it is committed without any legal justification against humanity if it is carried out as a systematic and widespread policy against an ethnic group or a specific group, so the study aimed to:

- *Measuring the displacement shock of the study sample.*
- *Identify the significance of the difference in displacement shock according to the gender variable (male-female).*
- *Measuring the attitude towards life of the study sample.*
- *Identifying the significance of the difference towards life according to the gender variable (male-female).*
- *Identifying the nature of the relationship between displacement shock and life orientation.*

As for the study instruments, the researcher used two criteria:

- *Displacement Trauma scale*
- *Life Orientation Scale*

To analyze the study data, the researcher used a set of statistical methods, including (Independent and Pearson correlation) testing.

The study reached the following results:

- *The study sample has a trauma from displacement*
- There is a difference between males and females in the trauma of displacement in favor of males.*
- *The study sample has a negative attitude towards life.*
- *There is a difference between male and female in Life Orientation and in favor of males.*
- *There is a statistically significant relationship between displacement and displacement trauma in the study sample.*

Introduction

The study Problem:

Forced displacement of the population is one of the grave violations under the Fourth Geneva Convention and under the Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court as being committed without any legal justification. It is a violation of humanity if it is committed as a systematic and widespread policy against a specific racial or ethnic group.

International law, including the United Nations Charter, has clear rules prohibiting the forced displacement of populations through the specific branches of international human rights law and other laws that have a clear relationship to human life.

The description of the phenomenon of displacement as trauma is due to the fact that it formed what is called an unforeseen and unprepared event, psychologically or intellectually, and therefore not known about it. In addition to the element of surprise, which constitutes the most important element of psychological trauma, or the state of panic and disorder that has dominated souls, if it becomes impossible to give an explanation of what is happening or speculate on what is to come. Compounding the state of fear and anxiety is the lack of knowledge of the nature, duration, and consequences of the risk.

It is known that psychological trauma does not disappear with the disappearance of the event that causes it, and it can continue for a long time after it, and the consequences of the trauma will be on all aspects of the social interaction of the exposed to the trauma.

The failure of the individual to achieve balance, and surrender to psychological trauma, and that it will be prey to psychological tensions and effectiveness, which leads to the formation of a negative attitude to life. This trend will negatively affect his personality, and become unstable, psychologically and socially unstable. Its proper psychological development decreases, and the performance required to achieve it becomes an unfulfilled

personality for itself, and does not enjoy the minimum mental health requirements and has negative relationships with others (Al-Salhi, 1985, p. 54).

The results of one of the studies at Harvard University indicated that individuals with a negative attitude towards life tend to excessively smoke, drink and weaken the immune system (Lennings 2000, pp. 161-181)

Durant believes that a negative view of life results in a tense mind, a pathological illness, and a completely empty life (Asaad, 1986, pp. 33--33).

Also the study of Arnaud (2016) found that there is a strong inverse relationship between life orientation and the avoidance personality (Arnaut, 2016, p. 69).

According to the Iraqi Ministry of Immigration and Immigrants / Information Department that the official sources and the International Committee of the Red Cross, between (1.8 million) people to (two million) are displaced inside Iraq. The feeling of surrender and helplessness in facing the pressures of life and creating a negative perception of life, and this may result in consequences that cannot be neglected.

In light of the foregoing, the current study problem arises through the following main question

- What is the relationship between the trauma of displacement and the trend towards life in the study sample?

The importance of the study:

No one can deny that pressures are inevitable that a person must face and be exposed to in the course of his life. The World Health Organization confirmed that 47% of all pressures experienced by individuals are entirely related to the circumstances surrounding (Al-Omari, 1994, p. 227)

The most prominent outcome of pressures are the shocks that the individual can be exposed to is the shock of fighting, war or displacement, and as a major cause of the spread of anxiety disorder among the population. Studies have indicated a high incidence of disturbances in areas that target disasters and wars (Al-Sheikh, 2002, p. 40).

Exposure of individuals to such conditions (fighting / war / displacement etc.) leads to the presence of symptoms resulting from the suddenness of the situation and the occurrence of a state of instability, which leads to this entrenching in the memory, which leads to the experience of the situation and the repetition of that coexistence by expressing this in issues related to situations Shocking, and may appear in the form of scary dreams, unaware of the content and distorted, as well as the presence of a continuous avoidance of stimuli associated with the traumatic situation, and a general dead response that did not exist before the shocking situation occurred (avoiding thoughts, feelings, conversations, activities, places and people), difficulty sleeping, and irregular food Such as loss of appetite, headache, abdominal pain, and the presence of sensory and psychological weakness resulting from the traumatic situation. (Thompson,1993,p107).

Has conducted(Kinchin, 1985)a study proves this as this study followed the symptoms that follow the traumatic situations. The study was conducted on a sample in Britain, and it was found that 50% of the sample suffers from symptoms that afflict traumatic situations, including sleep disorders that include nightmares, early recovery, anxiety and retrieved images about a trauma situation, distracted memory, forgetfulness and the appearance of weakness in the ability to pay attention and focus Subsequent psychological trauma leads to a decline in the cognitive level and shows forgetfulness, poor memory, an inability to complete, persistence, and work. Horowitz (1980) asserts that more than 75% of people with trauma suffer from these symptoms (Bresslau, 1991, p. 216).

According to the study of the World Health Organization, which described symptoms that include post-traumatic stresses from avoiding any stimuli reminiscent of traumatic situations, and insomnia with recurrent memories, the study clarified the factors that lead to symptoms of post-traumatic stresses and identified the severity of traumatic situations and the length of time the situation continues, The extent of the person's proximity, and we find that the symptoms of post-traumatic stress are evident in many studies and they affect the individual's memory of the danger, as he retrieves them because they affect his personality and his normal life and the individual may avoid any stimulus that leads him to remember that situation. The memory of the individual leads to reviving the past experience which It affects the future experiences of the individual. (Kessler, 1995, p.42)

Hence, the goal towards life is one of the psychological qualities that take place in the path of man and his future life, so it is the explosive who looks, and contemplates the occurrence of good, and what is better and better, he looks with an eye of hope, and sees the light, and seeks it unlike the pessimist who sees only Darkness, waiting only for failure and evil to happen, his vision of life seeing a black paralyzing movement, the energy shackle, (Dewberry, etal, 2000, P.731-738).

More (More, 2002) undertook an extensive study in order to explain the dynamism of the positive view of life, and concluded that it is an effective state, and a source of strength for the individual and society (More, 2002, P.237-265).

Through a positive view of life that the individual can create the conditions required for success by focusing on the possibilities and opportunities, and using them. An optimistic individual finds in every difficulty an opportunity, as he focuses on the pleasant and constructive aspects of life, avoids complaining, grumbling

about troubles, and frustrations he encounters in his life, as he can turn pitfalls into thresholds for progress (Albery, 1998, P.681-696).

A person with a positive approach is realistic, and positive in his way of thinking, thinking in a logical way. He does not confuse what he wishes, and what is real, for he is a person who matches the reality, works on its basis, and works through this reality to develop himself (Seligman, 2005, p. 35) .

(Scheier & Carver) assumes that there is a correlation between positive attitude towards life and attempts to deal with stress. When the positive people face difficulties, they make. (Scheier & Carver, 1987, p. 169-210).

also mentioned that the positive attitude towards life has a regular tendency for the individual to form important expectations for Sarah's results in the important areas of his life, as it is a concept characterized by motivating harmony. (Ben-Zur, etal, 2000,P:551-559)

(Taylor & Other, 1992) presented a study on the positive view of life, overcoming stress, compatibility, and healthy behavior when exposed to AIDS, and they found that there is a positive correlation between the positive view of life, overcoming psychological and social stresses and healthy harmony .. (Taylor & et, al 1992, pp. 460-473)

As the results of the study of(Fontaine, et, al, 1993) concluded, that the positive view of life is strongly associated with the perception of control with stress, with effective coping methods, and a reinterpretation of life situations (Fontaine & et, al, 1993, P: 19).

The results of the study (Abdel-Khaleq, 1998) also found a positive correlation between the attitude towards ... positive life, and the general health of the individual (Abdel-Khalek, 1998, pp. 3-9).

Also, the study (Abdullah, 2007) concluded that there is a positive correlation between the positive orientation of life and the source of internal control (Abdullah, 2007, p. 63).

(Rashid's study 2014) concluded that the current study sample has a negative attitude towards life and that there is a positive correlation between the orientation towards life and mental health (Rashid, 2014, p. C)

We can conclude the importance of the study with the following: -

In scientific terms:

The study of the two variables of the study (psychological trauma, the orientation towards life and the study sample) has a theoretical and scientific importance, because it clarifies the nature of the relationship between the individual and society and the fact that the study is the first according to the researcher's knowledge

- The scientific interpretation of this relationship will greatly reduce dependence on research and studies that have been conducted on such a relationship in other societies that differ in their conditions from the social conditions in Iraqi society if they exist.

Importance at the strategic and planning level:

The importance of the study from a strategic and planning point of view is as follows:

The results of this study, and the recommendations and suggestions that it draws, is an important tributary of drawing the strategy of the institutions concerned with the matter of the displaced families in order to take the necessary decisions accordingly and according to the results obtained.

Objectives of the study:

- 1- Measuring the displacement trauma of the study sample.
- 2- Identify the significance of the difference in displacement shock according to the gender variable (male-female)
- 3- Measuring the attitude towards life of the study sample.
- 4- Identifying the significance of the difference towards life according to the gender variable (male-female)
- 5- Identifying the nature of the relationship between displacement trauma and life orientation.

The limits of the study:

The current study is determined by the displaced families in the city of Baghdad in the year 2018.

Defining terms:

Displacement Trauma

It is the physical, cognitive, psychological, and social response of the individual as a result of his exposure to sudden experience (displacement) as a result of artificial crises (wars between countries or armed conflict within the country), and as a result, leaving the place of residence to avoid the effects of these dangerous conditions.

Life Orientation

The appetite for life and the belief in the possibility of fulfilling desires in the future. As well as believing in the possibility of goodness, or the good side of things instead of evil, or the bad side (Scheier & Carver, 1985, P: 219-247)

Theoretical background:

Two views were adopted in the current study:

- Hans Selye theory of displacement trauma, as the theory is comprehensive in its interpretation of psychological trauma, but here the presentation of the theory will be summarized for fear of prolonging and

focusing on important aspects that are related to the subject of the study and leave the generous reader further and detailing more of the theory in the scientific references that examined the topic of trauma and theory in detail.

• Scheier & Carver theory for life orientation as well as being a comprehensive and comprehensive theory, the researcher has adopted in his study the Scheier & Carver scale.

(Hans Selye) Theory

In (1956) interest began to study pressure when the Canadian physician and physician (Hans Selye) published his book entitled (The Stress of Life), (Wade & Tavris, 2003, p. 522).

Hans believes that stress is a condition that is manifested by a special syndrome consisting of all the excited changes within the individual's biological system (Selye, 1956, p. 54).

(Hans Selye) gave a description of the ways in which individuals react to pressure either with a good response (eustress) or a bad response (distress), because in both cases the physiological response is the same, in the case of good pressure (eustress) which indicates Happy and happy events such as holidays and marriage. We find that health and performance improve even when the pressure increases from this side, while in the case of bad pressure (distress), which refers to unpleasant or harmful pressure such as failure in the exam and severing the relationship with a person, we find that health and performance decrease on the other hand (Al- Quraishi, 2009, p. 56).

Stress-causing factors according to Hans Selye.

A- Physical psychological stress factors:

Such as disturbing sounds, injuries, wounds, physical pain, and accidents

B-psychological stress factors:

Such as anxiety, exhaustion, fears (of all kinds), dangers (especially life-threatening ones), loneliness and intellectual fatigue

C- Social stress factors:

Such as occupational struggles, difficult living conditions, family disputes, and difficulties in social relations (Al-Nabulsi, 1991, pp. 256-257).

According to (Hans Selye) post-traumatic psychological reactions can be evaluated into three stages: -

1 - The stage of warning or alerting: - It is represented by a reaction (a state of psychological alert) that is like a warning and is manifested in the individual honing his abilities and moving them in order to address the factors of stress.

2- The resistance phase: It is the near-term (first month) stage, and it comes to track its predecessor in the event of continuing stress factors, and it requires mobilizing all the capabilities of the body and developing defensive means and employing the behaviors and knowledge acquired to face the stress factors, and this stage is crucial because it enables the individual to the maximum The psychological stress that is generated from one period to another with the depletion of the power of self-defensive means, and its transformation into factors that support the perpetuation of the troubled symptoms, and here begins the chronic stage.

3 - The stage of stress and attrition (for exhaustion): It is the long-term stage (after a month or years) and is characterized by the exhaustion of the capabilities and efforts of the individual to adapt to the reality of the disaster and its dire moral and material consequences, which leads to the continued experience of psychological pressure, and this stage may lead to psychological disorders Acute can amount to severe depression, suicide, or schizophrenia, and if this stage lasts for a longer period of time, it can lead to death (Al-Nabulsi, 1995, p. 135).

Scheier & Carve Theory

(Scheier & Carver) hypothesized that positive feelings are related to the extent of movement and orientation towards goals and results, the more positive the results of goals, the more positive orientation toward life, and the opposite is true in relation to the negative orientation of life(Strack & ent, 1987p582-588,)

(Scheier & Carver) also stressed in their studies the importance of a positive view of life in order for a person to remain free from the dangers that can be destroyed by mental and physical health, through accumulated evidence, as it is beneficial for mental and physical health.(Schneider & Leitenberg,1989,p:7).

(Scheier & Carver) gave several aspects in which it can distinguish between individuals with a positive attitude towards life, and individuals with a negative approach to life. Through apparent rejection, lack of attention from the mental, and behavioral side to the goals assumed by external influences, (Change, 1998, p 1120).

Study procedures

Study community

The original community of the current research consists of forcibly displaced families in the city of Baghdad during the year (2017-2018).

The study sample

The current sample of the study was chosen by the presence of forcibly displaced persons and IDPs in the city of Baghdad in a random manner. It reached (292) from the following places:

- Baghdad Al Gadedah (Al-Sadiq Primary School / Rawdat Al-Muqdam / Al-Tumooh School / Al-Qahtaniya School)
 - Jamila (Abu Zar Al-Ghaffari School / Jalawla School)
 - Al-Shaab (Qatif School)
 - Al-Nahrawan (Nabi Yunus Complex)
 - Zizana camp to accommodate the displaced
 - A camp for the displaced in the university district
- Individuals distributed according to the following schedule:

Table (1)
Distribution of the study sample

N		Gender		Total
		Male	Female	
1	Baghdad Al Gadedah	51	34	85
2	Jamila	39	41	80
3	Al-Shaab	11	20	31
4	Al-Nahrawan	39	17	56
5	university district	15	9	24
6	Zizana camp	10	6	16
--	Total	165	127	292

Instruments of the study:

1- Displacement trauma Scale

The researcher built this scale, and the process of preparing it through the following steps: - statements formulation:

After defining the fear of social contact, in the light of that, the statements were collected and prepared and formulated according to the following steps:

A- Extracting a number of statements, by reviewing the literature that examined psychological trauma

B- Implementing a survey questionnaire that included a number of open questions about psychological trauma.

C- The statements that were obtained were collected and organized for number of (21) items, and the drafting of the statements took into account the following:

1- The statements should not be vague and its meaning be clear and specific

2- The statements should fit the nature of the sample

3- The statements of the scale should consist of negative and positive paragraphs

4- The statements should not be Suggestive

5- Avoid denying the negation in order to avoid confusion to the respondent

6- The sentences should be short sentence, so that the individual does not tire of answering them

7- The paragraphs should be coined with the conscience of the speaker

8- That the statements be representative of the daily life situations of individuals (Al-Imam, 1990, p. 325) & (Al-Zobaie, 1989, p. 96).

Measurement method:

Likert method was adopted in measurement, which is based on displaying a set of paragraphs to the respondent that includes verbal situations or information that the individual can be exposed to and asked to choose alternatives to the answer that expresses his opinion. This method is one of the common methods and followed in building psychological measures because they are distinguished by the following:

1- It is characterized by ease, construction and correction

2- The availability of a distinct scale. Smoothing his paragraphs

3- It gives the respondent more freedom to show the severity of his feelings towards the subject

4- It is characterized by flexibility and It is possible to build the scale according to it in a short time (Al-Imam., 1990, p. 325).

Scale instructions:

The instructions are the guide that guides the respondent while answering the phrases of each scale, and it was taken into consideration that the instructions are easy, simple and understandable. Because it was emphasized in the necessity of choosing the appropriate alternative respondent, who expresses his opinion, by putting a mark (✓) in front of the appropriate alternative, there is no correct and wrong answer. The answer will not be seen by anyone but the researcher, and will be used for the purposes of the study, so the respondent was asked not to mention his name.

Scale Correction:

It means setting the degree of response for each respondent on each of the statement of the scale, and then the total score for each questionnaire is extracted, by collecting degrees of response on the scale, and points were given to respond to the positive and negative statement of the scale in the light of the choices of the sample members for one of the alternatives. To achieve this Purpose, weights were given (5, 4, 3, 2, 1) to meet the alternatives to the answer (always applicable, often applied, sometimes applies, rarely applies, never apply), this is with respect to positive statement, while negative paragraphs were given weights (1, 2, 3, 4, 5) respectively.

The pilot study:

After setting the instructions for the scale of the displacement trauma and the direction towards life, the pilot study was conducted to find out the degree of clarity of the scale statement of the study community. The difficulties that the respondent could face to avoid before applying it in his final form and to know the time it takes for the sample members to answer the scale, so the two scales were applied to a sample that reached (31). After conducting the pilot study and reviewing the answers, it became clear that all statement of the two scales are clear among the individuals of the sample, and the average time taken by the respondent in answering the two scales is (35) minutes.

The application of the two scales:

The researcher applied both scales to the individuals of the study sample on the areas that contain the displaced families mentioned above and was keen to collect all the forms from the respondents.

Statement analysis:

(Ebel) indicates that the goal of paragraph analysis is to keep good statement on the scale (Ebel, 1972, p. 392).

The quality of the test depends to the maximum on the statements that make up it, and it is necessary in the best applications to analyze each Statement, in order to keep those Statements that fit the goals and rationale for which the tool was built. So, the analysis of statements is an integral part of both the validity and reliability of the test (Freeman, 1962, p. 112-113).

In order to calculate the discriminatory strength of the statements, and after the completion of the displacement trauma scale, the final numbers of (292) forms of the displacement trauma scale were obtained.

1- Statement analysis of the displacement trauma scale using the Extreme Groups method.

The calculation of the discriminatory power of each Statement is the ability of the Statement to distinguish between individuals who have a high score in the scale and those who have a low score in it (Mehrense & Lehman, 1973, p. 328).

After applying the scale and for the purpose of retaining the distinct statement, the statement analysis was performed using the method of the two extremist groups by following the following steps:

1- Determining the total score for each of the 292 forms.

2- Arranging the forms from highest to lowest.

3- Appointing (27%) of the forms that obtained the higher degrees and the number (79) forms, as well as assigning (27%) of the forms that obtained the lower degrees and the number (79) forms, and thus the number of the forms that were subject to the analysis (158) form Out of (292) forms.

4- Applying the T-Test for two independent samples to test the significance of the differences between the upper and lower groups on each statement, and the T value was considered an indication for distinguishing each statement by comparing it with the tabular value of (2.62) at the significance level (0.01) and with a degree of freedom (156) All statements were distinct. Table (2) includes the mean and the standard deviation for each of the scale Statements for the upper and lower groups and the calculated T value for them.

Table (2)

Statement discrimination coefficient of displacement trauma Scale in the style of the two extremist groups

No Statement	High groups		Low groups		T value	Result
	mean	SD	mean	SD		
1	3.80	0.525	3.22	0.900	5.725	Significant
2	3.20	0.862	2.44	1.187	5.380	Significant
3	3.13	0.928	2.17	1.132	6.838	Significant
4	3.69	0.520	2.84	1.104	7.257	Significant
5	3.59	0.656	2.25	1.145	10.573	Significant
6	2.56	1.162	1.68	1.022	5.970	Significant
7	3.75	0.532	3.25	0.978	4.669	Significant

8	3.69	0.679	2.91	1.196	5.877	Significant
9	3.79	0.512	3.19	0.978	5.666	Significant
10	3.53	0.716	2.36	1.131	9.055	Significant
11	3.07	0.872	2.02	1.014	8.203	Significant
12	3.29	0.918	2.31	1.133	6.931	Significant
13	2.56	1.255	1.82	1.031	4.740	Significant
14	3.68	0.639	3.02	1.041	5.594	Significant
15	3.19	0.939	2.03	0.971	8.905	Significant
16	3.83	0.421	3.13	1.077	6.322	Significant
17	3.24	1.101	2.10	1.207	7.244	Significant
18	3.57	0.751	2.78	1.113	6.161	Significant
19	3.93	0.297	3.50	0.848	4.926	Significant
20	3.52	0.717	3.06	0.950	3.962	Significant
21	3.30	0.960	2.01	1.140	8.977	Significant

Psychometric properties of the displacement shock meter

Validity

(Anastasi) believes that an honest measure is the scale that fulfills the function for which it is prepared (Anastasi, & Urbina, 1988, p. 139).

Validity refers to the degree to which the scale is able to actually measure the property that it is supposed to have measured, and in other words, does the scale really measure what was prepared to measure it.

Construct Validity:

The Validity of construction is one of the most acceptable types of Validity, and a large number of specialists believe that it is consistent with the essence of the (Ebel) concept of Validity in terms of saturation of the scale in the general sense of the phenomenon being measured (Al-Imam, 1990, p. 131). This was achieved through the following:

1- Statement degree and its relationship to the overall degree:

This means that the statement measures the same concept that the scale measures as a whole, as this is one of the indicators of the Validity of construction (Al-Zobaie et al., 1981, p. 43).

This type of validity in the displacement trauma scale was achieved by finding the correlation between the degree of each vertebra and the overall degree of the scale, and Pearson correlation coefficient was used.

The results of the statistical treatment of the individual's scores on the displacement shock scale showed a significant correlation when compared to the tabular value, at the level of significance (0.01) and the degree of freedom (291) and for all paragraphs, Table (3) and it shows that.

Table (3)

statement degree correlation coefficients with the overall degree of displacement trauma scale

No	discrimination Coefficient
1	0.395
2	0.418
3	0.431
4	0.435
5	0.451
6	0.334
7	0.431
8	0.498
9	0.467
10	0.424
11	0.417
12	0.692
13	0.791
14	0.659
15	0.521
16	0.591
17	0.618
18	0.521

19	0.651
20	0.347
21	0.571

Reliability:

Reliability indicates whether the measurement procedures give the same values for the measured property each time it is measured, or is the extent to which the test is consistent with itself in measuring which side it measures. A fixed measure gives the same results if it is applied to the same individuals again (Barron, 1976, p. 418).

It was adopted to calculate the Reliability of the scale:

1- Internal Consistency:

The Reliability coefficient extracted in this way indicates the internal correlation between the scale vertebrae and has been extracted in a way:

A - Split-half

In this method (292) forms were used, then the displacement shock meter paragraphs were divided into two halves, then according to the Pearson correlation coefficient between the two halves of the scale. The reliability coefficient before the correction was (0.71), and since the correlation coefficient extracted was for half of the scale, it was corrected using an equation (Spearman - Brown) after the correction (0.830), and it is a high reliability coefficient.

B- Alfa Coefficient for Internal Consistency:

This method relies on the consistency of individuals' performance from one paragraph to another (Thorndike & Hagen, 1989, p. 79).

To calculate reliability in this way, the alpha equation was used, and the reliability coefficient of the displacement shock meter was (0.839).

2- External consistency factor:

Test-Reset Method

Verkson(1991) emphasizes that extracting the reliability factor in this way is by reapplying the measuring instrument twice and in two different times or times to the same group of individuals(Verkson, 1991, p. 517).

Then find the correlation coefficient between the two applications, where this correlation coefficient represents a measure of stability (Mehrens & Lehmann, 1973, p. 109).

Reliability was extracted in this way to the displacement shock scale, and the scale was re-applied to a sample of (16) individuals where Adames (1964) indicates that the re-application of the scale to know its stability must be within a period of less than two weeks.(Adams,1964,p.58).

Then calculate the Pearson correlation coefficient between the scores of individuals in the first application and their degrees in the second application. The coefficient of persistence in this way was used to measure the fear of social contact, and the degree of correlation between the first and second applications was (0.75).

Life orientation scale

The researcher adopted the scale of (Scheier & Carver) the Arabic version and the Arabized by Hadi (2008), which consists of (12) statements. The validity and consistency were extracted by the two methods of apparent honesty and sincerity of construction. Its value was (0.93).

The results of the study and its interpretation

We will present a review of the results reached based on the data collected according to the sequence of the objectives of the study. It also includes the interpretation and discussion of the results in the light of the theory adopted, then the recommendations and the proposals as follows:

The first Objective: - Measuring the displacement trauma.

To achieve this goal, the mean was calculated for the scores of individuals who number (292) displaced men on the collective horror scale, and it was found that the mean was (81.54) degrees, and a standard deviation of (9,371) degrees, and by comparing this average with the hypothetical average of the scale that It reached (63) degrees, it is clear that it is higher than the hypothetical average(0.01) and degree of freedom (291), and Table (4) shows that

Table (4)

T-test to indicate the difference between the sample mean and the hypothetical mean on the displacement trauma scale

sample	Mean	SD	hypothetical mean	T value	Tabular T	Level of sig

291	81.54	9.371	63	33.832	2.626	0.01
-----	-------	-------	----	--------	-------	------

When looking at the above table, the following is evident: -

- 1- When comparing the sample mean with the hypothetical mean of the scale, we find that the sample mean for the scale is higher than the hypothetical average
- 2- This difference statistically significant at 0.01 level.
- 3- We conclude that the study sample has a trauma from displacement.

The second Objective: to identify the significance of the statistical difference in displacement trauma, according to the gender variable (Male- Female).

To achieve this goal, the mean of the sample scores of the male (165) males and the mean of the female sample (127) females was extracted. The mean of the male sample was (46.91) and with a standard deviation of (5.654) and the mean of the female sample (34.63) with a deviation Standard (3.717). To test the statistical significance between the two means, the T-test was used for two independent samples. The calculated T value (85.58) was at the significance level (0.01) and the degree of freedom (290). It was found to be statistically significant, which indicates a difference between males and females in the study sample in the trauma of displacement and in favor of males (according to the rule of the arithmetic mean) and table (5) illustrates this.

Table (5)
T test for the significance of the difference in displacement trauma according to the gender variable (male - female)

sample	number	Mean	SD	T value	Tabular T	Level of sig
males	165	46.91	5.654	8.587	2.58	Significant
females	127	34.63	3.717			

The third Objective: measuring the orientation towards life.

To achieve this goal, the arithmetic mean for the scores of individuals whose number is (292) was abandoned on the scale of life orientation, and it was found that the mean was 31.923 degrees, with a standard deviation of (6.127) degrees, and by comparing this average with the hypothetical average of the scale that reached (36) degrees, it is clear that it is higher than the hypothetical average, and to test the significance of this difference statistically, the researcher used the T-test for one sample ((One-Sample T- Test) and it was found that the calculated T value reached (11.388) degrees which is statistically significant at the level of significance (0.01) and degree Freedom (292), and Table (6) illustrates this

Table (6)
T-test for the significance of the difference between the sample mean and the hypothetical mean on the scale of life orientation

Sample	Mean	SD	hypothetical mean	T value	Tabular T	Level of sig
291	28.63	5.127	36	24.56	2.58	0.01

When looking at the above table, the following is evident: -

- 1- When comparing the mean of the sample with the hypothetical mean of the scale, we find that the hypothetical mean of the scale is higher than the mean of the sample
- 2- This difference statistically significant at 0.01 levels.
- 3-We conclude that the study sample has a negative trend towards life, since the mean of the study sample is less than the hypothetical mean

The Fourth Objective: To identify the significance of the difference in the orientation towards life according to the gender variable (male - female).

To achieve this goal, the mean for the sample scores of the male sample (165) displaced and the female sample (127) were displaced, and the mean for the male population was (31,313), with a standard deviation of (6,154)

and the mean female sample (25,947) with a standard deviation of (4.1). To test the statistical significance between the two means, the T-test was used for two independent samples (T-Test) and the calculated T value was (11.924) at the significance level (0.01) and the degree of freedom (290) and it was found that it is statistically significant, which indicates a difference between male and female (According to the rule of the arithmetic mean, the interpretation of this result is the same as the interpretation of the result of the second goal, as mentioned, and table (7) shows that

Table (7)

T-test for the significance of the difference in orientation towards life according to the gender variable (male - female)

sample	number	mean	SD	T value	Tabular T	Level of sig
males	165	31.313	6.154	11.924	2.58	0.01
females	127	25.947	4.1			

The Fifth Objective: To know the relationship between displacement shock and life orientation.

In order to identify the relationship between displacement shock and life orientation in the study sample, the researcher applied the Pearson correlation coefficient between the degrees of displacement shock and the degrees of life orientation for the individuals of the sample number (292) persons. The correlation coefficient between them reached (0.738), and the (Correlation coefficient T test) was used extract the T-value of the correlation coefficient has reached (18.60) and when compared to the tabular value at the level of significance (0.05) and degree of freedom (290) it showed that it is statistically significant, which indicates a strong and positive correlation between two variables . And Table (8) illustrates this.

Table (8)

Correlation coefficient and T value between displacement trauma and life orientation

Variables	sample	R	T value	Tabular T	Level of sig
displacement trauma and life orientation	290	0.738	18.60	0.11	0.05

When looking at the above table, it appears that there is a positive correlation between the variable of displacement trauma and the orientation towards life in the study sample, that is, the more individuals feel the psychological trauma of displacement, the greater the negative orientation towards life.

Results:

- With regard to the first objective, which showed the feeling of the study sample about the trauma of displacement, the result can be explained according to the theory (Hans Selye), which holds that individuals are exposed to a group of stresses (physical psychological stress factors - psychological stress factors - social stress factors) that together constituted a stressor on The entity and stability of the individual resulted in a bad response from it (distress) to the situation. This was represented by the individual feeling the psychological trauma caused by the displacement.

- Statistical treatments indicated that there is a statistical difference between males and females in the trauma of displacement and the statistical difference in favor of males, and that males in Iraqi society have a great responsibility in maintaining family cohesion and providing daily living necessities. Because the occurrence of displacement led to increased psychological and social pressure on them, which this increased their sense of trauma of displacement, and he himself interpreted the fourth goal.

- When measuring the life orientation of the sample, it was found that the male and female sample had a negative attitude towards life according to (Scheier & Carver) assumption that the negative feelings are related to the extent of movement and the orientation towards the goals and results, the more negative the results of the goals, the greater the negative attitude towards life.

The conditions of the displaced people suffer from bad conditions and different pressures from the scarcity of daily resources such as food, drink, and clothing, as well as housing, the deterioration of the economic condition of most of them. The spread of unemployment and diseases, which led to creating a negative feeling towards life and this is a danger that the negative feeling of not accepting life leads to dire consequences, including suicide the prevalence of crime and moral deviance.

- Pearson correlation between the trauma of displacement and the orientation towards life that there is a strong relationship between them and this confirms that social conditions and events play a negative and dangerous role in the social life of individuals. Because the frequent exposure to situations of a negative nature that threatens the existence of the human being makes the individual shows some behavioral indicators outside the social norms, which may reach some of these dangerous manifestations to threaten the social entity and its sustainability through the prevalence of crime, theft, family and social disintegration, and other threats to the safety of the human community.

Recommendations and proposals:

Recommendations:

Government institutions and civil society organizations that are related to the situation of the displaced make more efforts to care for the displaced and provide their needs and requirements to alleviate them and reduce the sense of trauma of their displacement in order to motivate them emotionally to create a positive orientation towards life.

The proposals:

- Conducting the study variables on other samples from the displaced community (teenagers - university students..etc).
- Using of some demographic variables for the current research, such as (age - socio-economic level).

References:

- Abdel-Khalek, Ahmed Mohamed, (1998) Principles of Mental Health, University Knowledge House Presentation of Dr. Louis Kamel Malikia in the specialized psychological culture magazine, No. (25), volume (7), Beirut, Arab Renaissance House, Beirut, Lebanon.
- Abdullah, Muhammad Qasim, (2007): An Introduction to Mental Health, Dar Al Fikr Publishing, Amman, Jordan.
- Adams , G. (1964) : Measurement and Evaluation in Education Psychology and Guidance , New York, Holt
- Albery, N. E, (1998): The roles of constructive Thinking and Optimism in Psychological and behavioral adjustment during pregnancy, Journal of Personality and Social psychology. 73.
- Al-Nabulsi, Muhammad Ahmad (1991): psychological trauma, disaster science and war, the Arab Renaissance Publishing House, Beirut.
- Al-Nabulsi, Muhammad Ahmad (1995): Towards Arab Psychology, Al-Tale'a Publishing House, Beirut
- Al-Omari, Ibrahim (1979): Human Behavior, Alexandria, Egyptian Universities House.
- Al-Quraishi, Ali Turki Nafil (2009). Chronic Social Stress and its Relationship with Absorption and Dissociative Experiences among University Students, the council of college of Arts, Baghdad University as a partial requirement to gain a Ph.D Literature in Psychology.
- Al-Salhi, Najdat Qasim, (1985): Mental Health, Institute of Educational Training and Development, Ministry of Education, Baghdad
- Al-Sheikh, Rawa'a Saleh Nuri (2002), some symptoms associated with post-disorder Shock pressures and their relationship to some variables, the amount of arts, Al-Mustansiriya University, Master Thesis, unpublished. Iraq.
- Al-Zobaie, Abdul Jalil Ibrahim and Al-Kinani, Ibrahim and Bakr, Muhammad Elias (1981): Psychological tests and measurements, University of Mosul, Mosul.
- Anastasi .A, & Urbina .S, (1979), psychological testing ,7th printice, Hill .
- Arnaut, Bushra Ismail (2016): The Orientation toward Life and its Relationship to Personality Disorder, Psychological Guidance Journal, Psychological Guidance Center, Issue 45, pp. 38-82, Cairo.
- Asaad, Youssef Michael, (1986): optimism and pessimism, the Egyptian Renaissance, Cairo, Arab Republic of Egypt.
- Ben-Zur, A., (2000) : Coping strategies, live style changes, and pessimism after .pen-heart surgery. Health- Soc-Work, 2000 Aug, 25(3)pp551-960, palestain.
- Bresslau , N (1991): Traumatic events and posttraumatic stress Disorder in an urban population of young adults, Journal of general psychiatry, vol . 48 , n . 5.

- Change, E. (1998): Dispositional optimism and primary and secondary Appraisal of stressor controlling for confounding influences and relations to coping: and psychological and physical adjustment, *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* 74 (4) . PP1109-1120 .
- Dewberry, C.K. Ing, M. James, S. Nixon, M., & Richardson, S. (2000): Anxiety and optimism, *Journal of Social Psychology*
- Eble, R. (1972): *Essential of Education Measurement*, New Jersey, Prentice-Hall Company.
- Fontaine, K.R. Manstead A.S & Wagner H. (1993): Optimism perceived control over stress and coping European, *Journal of Personality*.
- Freeman, F. S. (1962): *Theory and practice of psychological testing*, Holt, Rinehart & Winston, New York.
- Kessler, R. 1995, Post traumatic stress disorder in national comorbidity survey, *Journal of General Psychiatry* vol. 52, N. 12 .
- Lennings-C-J. (2000): Optimism satisfaction and time perspective in the Elderly, in *Int-J Aging - Hum-Dev*, 51(3), pp167-181, D.S.A.
- Mehrens, W.A. & Lehman, L.J. (1973): *Measurement and Evaluation in Education and Psychology*, Holt Rinehart and Winston, New York.
- More, J. (2002): Dynamic optimism and Extroversion cognitive – Emotion a virtue, *Journal of Personality* 55-237-265 .
- Rashid, Nabil Abbas (2014): Orientation towards life and its relationship to mental health among political prisoners, Al-Mustansiriyah University, College of Arts, unpublished master's thesis, Iraq.
- Scheier, M. F., & Carver, C. S. (1987): Dispositional optimism and physical well-being: the influence of generalized outcome expectancies on health *Journal of Personality*
- Scheier, M. F. & Carver, C. S. (1985): Optimism, coping and health: Assessment and implications of generalized outcome expectancies, New Jersey.
- Schneider, M.J., & Leitenberg, H. (1989): "A comparison of aggressive and children's self – Esteem optimism and pessimism, and Causal attributions for success and failure," *Journal of Abnormal Child Psychology*. Vol.17, No.2, 135-142.
- Seligman, Martin, (2005): *Learn Optimism*, translated by Dar Jarir for Publishing and Distribution, Cairo, Arab Republic of Egypt.
- Selye, H. (1956). *The stress of life*. New York. McGraw-Hill.
- Strack, S., Carver, C. S. & Blaney, P. H. (1987): Predicting success following completion of an after care program following treatment for alcoholism, the Role of Dispositional optimism, *The Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*.
- Taylor, S. E., Kemeny, M. E., Aspiwall, G., Schneider, S. G., Ropdriguez, R., & Herber M. (1992). Optimism, Coping, Psychological distress, and high-risk sexual behavior among men at risk for AIDS. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*.
- Thompson, M. (1993): Age difference in the psychological consequences of Hurricanes Hugo. *Psychology and Aging*, Vol. 8, n. 3.
- Thorndike, Robert, and Elizabeth, Heijer (1989): *Measurement and Evaluation in Psychology and Education*, translation: Abdullah Zaid Al-Kilani and Abdel Rahman Adas, The Jordan Book Center, Amman, Jordan.
- Verkson, George (1991): *Statistical Analysis in Education and Psychology*. Translated by Hana Al-Okaili, Dar Al-Hekma for Printing and Publishing, Al-Mustansiriyah Ministry of Higher Education.
- Wade, Carole & Tavris, Carol. (2003): *Psychology*. Prentice-Hall, Inc. Englewood cliffs, New Jersey.
- Al-Imam, Mustafa Mahmoud and others (1990): *Measurement and Evaluation*, Dar Al-Hekma Press, Cairo.
- Brown, F.G. (1976): *Principles of Education and Psychological testing*, New York Wiley.

Author Information

Zalzal Mahmood Abass

Al-Mustansiriyah University / College of Arts /
Department of Psychology
